

QUIZ**LAST NAME: KHAMIS****FIRST NAME: MOHAMED****PROGRAM CODE: MBASD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr.GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice 365

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following is a good reason to avoid plagiarism?

- Your teacher will be disappointed in you.
- It is not ethical to steal someone else's words or ideas.
- You could get a zero on your paper.
- All of the above.**¹

2. When do we not cite something?

- When using quotes from another source.

¹ Euclid University. ACA-401 Coursepack: Period1. Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015, 10. Accessed February 2 2020 from <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1>

- When the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas you do not need to cite its source.²**
- When using paraphrase or statistic data from another source.
- Not of the above.
3. **Which one of the following is the primary source of information?**
- Interview.³**
- Articles from magazines.
- Textbooks.
- Reference books, including dictionaries, encyclopedias, and atlases.
4. **Which of the following sentences uses the comma incorrectly?**
- He is the man, whom I met on the plane.⁴**
- He is strong, healthy man.
- I need to buy a dress, so I am going to the mall.
- All of the above.

² Ibid, 30.

³ Sebranek Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. Write Source 2000. Massachusetts: a Houghton Mifflin Company, 1999, 277. Accessed February 2 2020 from <http://libraryguides.bennett.edu/home/writing/chicago-turabian-style/turabian-style-in-text-parenthetical-citations--reference-list>

⁴ Ibid, 389.

5. **Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations documents what citation style?**

Chicago.⁵

MLA.

ACA.

APA.

6. **Which of the following statements is the reason for citing sources?**

To give a credit.

To assure readers about the accuracy of your facts.

To show readers the research tradition that informs my work.

All of the above.⁶

7. **In which of the following paper writing does not allow to use direct quotes?**

Literature.

History.

current events.

Science.⁷

⁵ Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and the University of Chicago press additional staff, eighth edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013, 1.

⁶ Turabian, 86.

⁷ Euclid University. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press 2015, 5. Accessed February 2 2020 from <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-4>.

8. **Which of these should you look for when proofreading?**
- Capital letters in the wrong place.
 - Spelling errors.
 - Missing words.
 - All of the above.**⁸
9. **What language is used for European Commission rule of style?**
- American English.
 - Australian English.
 - South Africa English.
 - British English.**⁹
10. **How you can write numbers in words or figures, using European Commission rule of style?**
- First consideration should be consistency within a passage.
 - Write low numbers up to nine in words and larger numbers (10 and above) in figures.
 - If the passage contains both kinds, use either figures or words for all the numbers.
 - All of the above.**¹⁰

⁸ Ibid, 7.

⁹ European Commission Directorate General for Translation. English Style Guide, A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission, 2011, 11. Accessed February 2 2020 from

¹⁰ Ibid, 28.

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